

Phase Transfer Catalysis in the Polycondensation Processes. VII. Synthesis of Polyethers from 3,3-Bis(chloromethyl)oxetane and 4,4'-Dihydroxyazobenzene

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Manuscript received 25 September 1992, revised 30 August 1993, accepted 29 September 1993

The phase transfer catalysis (PTC) has been widely used in synthesis of polyethers¹⁻⁵. This method is adequate to obtain linear polymers with ordered structure, which may exhibit liquid crystalline (LC) properties^{1,4,5}.

This communication presents the possibility of synthesis of polyethers starting from 4,4'-dihydroxyazobenzene (DHAB) and 3,3-bis(chloromethyl)oxetane (BCMO) by PTC in liquid/liquid system. The LC properties of the polymer have also been analysed.

Results and Discussion

The polycondensation of BCMO with DHAB under the phase transfer conditions may be represented by the reaction,

The structures of both the commonomers were identified by ir and nmr spectra. Thus, the nmr spectrum reveals two signals at δ 4.5 and 4.75 (hydrogens in oxetane ring) and two large signals at δ 7.0-8.5 (benzene ring protons). The ir spectrum reveals characteristic bands at 1 500, 1 600 (benzene ring), 950 (oxetane ring) 1 210-1 230 cm^{-1} (ether linkages).

Unlike the other synthesised polyethers^{4,5}, the BCMO-DHAB polymer has been obtained only

in nitrobenzene aqueous NaOH two-phase system. The other tested organic solvents showed a low activity in the polycondensation (Table 1) even though some of them have high dielectric constants. It might be that the polymer solubility in the organic solvent plays an important role. It is worth mentioning that the polyether has a good solubility in nitrobenzene.

TABLE 1-ROLE OF ORGANIC SOLVENT IN POLYCONDENSATION OF BCMO WITH DHAB

Temp. = 85°, time = 5 h, [DHAB] = [BCMO] = 0.266 mol dm⁻³, PTC = TEBA, [DHAB]/[TEBA] = 4/1.6 molar

Solvent	Dielectric constant	Polymer yield %
Nitrobenzene	43.5	72.3
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	9.9	0.7
Dimethylsulphoxide	-	0.3
Methylethylketone	31.8	1.2
Toluene	12.0	0
Monochlorobenzene	5.9	2.3

TEBA and TBHS appear to be the most efficient PT catalysts. All the other tested catalysts show very low activity even they have a bulky

TABLE 2-CATALYSTS EFFICIENCY IN BCMO-DHAB POLYETHERIFICATION

Temp. = 85°, time = 5 h, [BCMO] = [DHAB] = 0.266 mol dm⁻³, solvent : nitrobenzene, [BCMO]/[PTC] = 4/1.6 molar

Catalyst	TEBA	TBHS	TMAC	TEAC	TPMPC	CPyAB	None
Polymer yield (%)	72.3	74.6	4.7	5.4	1.1	2.5	0

or small organic radicals (Table 2). Concentration of the catalyst has no significant influence upon the reaction. The increase in polymer yield was not so important when more than 1 : 1 catalyst (TEBA) to monomer molar ratio was used.

The time-conversion and conversion temperature curves (time vs polymer yield curves) show that the monomers are rapidly consumed in the first 4–5 h and then conversion levels off at around 70–80% polymer yield. The polycondensation of BCMO with DHAB proved to be very sensitive to concentration of the alkaline solution. The highest polymer yields are obtained when 15*N* NaOH solution is used. At lower or more concentrated alkaline solution, the conversion drops drastically.

The synthesised polyethers showed anisotropic properties in the melt state. The DSC thermograms for the polymer obtained at 85° for 5 h reveal several transitions from which that at 59° (55° on the second scan) might be the glass transition temperature. All the other mark mesophasic transitions and are located at 101, 150, 200° and isotropisation at 225°. After cooling and rescanning there remain three thermal transitions (100, 170, 196°) followed by isotropisation at 220° which was confirmed also in polarising microscopy. Fig. 1 presents images of this sample at 200°. It is worth mentioning that the thermal transitions associated with the azo-polyether are less outlined compared to those registered for other polymers

Fig. 1. Optical polarisation micrograph of the BCMO/DHAB polyether at 200° (×100)

based on BCMO^{4,5}.

The results outline the possibility of obtaining polyethers from BCMO and DHAB under the TPC conditions, which reveal liquid-crystalline properties. Their thermal transitions are less pronounced and this may suggest a smectic texture in these polymers.

Experimental

BCMO³ and DHAB-*trans*⁶ were prepared by reported methods. The solvents (Fluka, AG) and PT-catalysts (Merck) were used as such. The following PT-catalysts were used : tetramethylammonium chloride (TMAC), tetraethylammonium chloride (TEAC), triethylbenzylammonium chloride (TEBA), tetrabutylammonium hydrogen sulphate (TBHS), triphenylmethylphosphonium chloride (TPMPC) and cetylpyridylammonium bromide (CPyAB).

In a typical polycondensation reaction, DHAB (4 mmol) dissolved in 15*N* NaOH aqueous solution (15 ml) was mixed with nitrobenzene (15 ml) containing BCMO (4 mmol). After a vigorous stirring of the two phases, PT-catalyst (2 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was heated at 85° for 5 h, then the content cooled and poured in two-fold excess of acidified (HCl) methanol. The isolated polymer was filtered off, washed successively with water and methanol and dried under reduced pressure at 40°.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss-Jena UR-20 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL-60 MHz instrument. A Du Pont-2000 DSC V4 differential scanning calorimeter was used to determine the thermal transitions which were read at the maximum of the endothermic or exothermic peaks. The investigation in polarised light was carried out on a VEB-analytic apparatus.

References

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